

PREDICTION OF FAILURE BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE LATTICE STRUCTURE UNDER COMPRESSIVE LOAD

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ABSTRACT

The composite lattice structures are mainly applied to launch vehicles and are designed to endure compressive load. Specific modulus and strength of this structure are high, but there are many defect due to manufacturing problems. Verification of the analytical model is essential because the difference of strength between design and actual structure may cause problems during operation. However, the full scale test is difficult because time and space are limited. Since the shape of structure is complex, physical properties test for sub-element is also difficult. Therefore, a test method for unit cell specimen is required. In this paper, compression test of single unit cell was performed. Maximum failure load and strain at failure were measured by universal testing machine and strain gauges. Buckling and static analysis were performed and compared with the test results. Strain and elastic modulus of unit cell was compared with the results of test and finite element analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

The composite lattice structures are mainly used for cylindrical aerospace structures subjected to compressive load. Because they are lattice-shaped, they can be manufactured with low weight and can save costs. They also have the advantage of high specific modulus and strength. These structures are used for aircraft fuselages, structural links of launch vehicles and pairings. The one most commonly used is launch vehicle. When the launch vehicle lifts off, it is mainly used to support the compressive load. These structures are fabricated by the filament winding technique and each ribs are same thickness and unidirectional. Therefore, there are some variations of the fiber volume fraction between the rib and the knot region where the ribs and ribs intersect, and the thickness of each plies are also different. In addition, since the ply must be overlapped, many voids and defects occur in the knot region. Such a problem may cause the stiffness and strength of the structure to deteriorate, and structural reliability may become problems. Therefore, examination for failure behaviour of composite lattice structure under compressive load is essential. However, the full scale test requires a high-capacity testing machine so that it is limited to space, time and cost. Therefore, it is necessary to test sub-element of lattice structure for verifying the analytical model.

Since ribs are curved and twisted, the tensile and compressive tests for the strength and stiffness of each rib are difficult. Terashima et al. [1] have conducted bending and compression test of sub-element and established the design and manufacturing guideline. Aoki et al. [2] also have conducted compression test of unit cell specimen which have various thicknesses. Buragohain et al. [3] have performed test of the miniature model and confirmed the buckling shape and it was compared with the analysis. Totaro et al. [4] have examined design and manufacturing of composite lattice structures in micromechanics. In this study, sub-elements of composite lattice structures are prepared as single unit cell and compression tests were performed. The maximum load and failure mode of single unit cell were also examined. Finite element analysis was performed to compare test models. Compressive modulus and strength were examined by measured strain and load.

2 COMPRESSION TEST

Figure 1 shows composite lattice model and single unit cell for compression test. The strains in longitudinal direction of helical rib were measured by strain gauges attached to the side of the helical

rib. Since the top and bottom surface of the specimen was not uniform, glass fabric tab was attached to top and bottom surface of the specimen to apply load uniformly. And glass fabric tab constrains the deformation of hoop rib because deformation in circumferential direction of the hoop rib of full scale structure does not occur.

Figure 1: Composite lattice full scale model(left) and Single unit cell(right).

Figure 2 is the jig for compression test. It was designed to apply pure compressive load, to prevent buckling in the out-of-plane direction and to fix the specimen. Figure 3 shows set-up for compression test. The compression test was conducted by using universal testing machine(INSTRON 5882 : 100kN capacity). Since there is no standard for the test conducted in this study, the test was conducted by crosshead displacement rate of 1.3 mm/min referring to standard compression test method for composite laminates – ASTM D6641 [5]. Load and displacement were measured by using UTM and strain was measured by using multi-channel strain amplifier(HBM.MGCPlus).

Figure 2: Jig for compression test.

Figure 3: Compression test set-up.

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS MODEL

Finite element analysis was performed using MSC.NASTRAN. 2D shell laminate element was used and physical properties of test results were applied to material properties. In order to apply the boundary conditions of the test specimen, a rigid body element was used as shown in Figure 4. Bottom of model was fixed and entire model was constrained in out-of-plane direction. The number of layers of knots is twice that of ribs, and the thickness of each layer is twice that of knots. As shown in Figure 5, the ply and resin layers were separated because the thickness of each part was different and it make modeling the connection part difficult [2]. Therefore, the fiber volume fraction of knots was twice that of ribs. Stacking sequence of knots and ribs is $[0/Resin]_{17}$ and $[32/-32]_{17}$ respectively as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Finite element model of single unit cell.

Figure 5: Stacking sequence of each part.

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

As a result of the compression test of single unit cell, the failure of ribs were observed near the end of helical rib as shown in Figure 6. So, it was thought that helical rib is most vulnerable to compressive force. Figure 7 shows the load-displacement curve of single unit cell and it was confirmed that the failure occurred primarily before the maximum load. The average of the primary failure is -30.38kN and the maximum load is -35.31kN. Since rib was sufficiently thick, the out-of-plane buckling did not occur in this test. In order to confirm about failure mode, buckling analysis was performed and Figure 8 shows in-plane buckling mode. The in-plane buckling mode consistent with the test boundary conditions is 2nd mode and critical buckling load is 232.35kN. And in load-displacement curve of Figure 7, there is no flatten curve that indicate buckling. Therefore, it is confirmed that the failure load due to compression is lower than the critical buckling load.

Figure 6: Failure mode of single unit cell.

Figure 7: Load-Displacement curve of single unit cell.

	CT#4	CT#11	CT#14	Avg.
Primary failure load (kN)	-32.21	-29.05	-29.87	-30.38
Max. load (kN)	-34.26	-40.68	-30.99	-35.31

Table 1: Test results of single unit cell

Figure 8: In-plane buckling mode.

Figure 9 shows the load-strain curve of each specimen. Comparing the values of gauges 1 and 2, it can be seen that the load was initially unbalanced.

Figure 9: Load-Strain curve of single unit cell.

Finite element analysis was performed and load of 20kN was applied for comparison with the test results. The compressive modulus in longitudinal direction of helical rib was calculated by using the strain, and the results of analysis and test were compared. Comparing the gauges 2 and 3, it was confirmed that helical rib deformed by compressive and bending load. So, compressive and bending strain were calculated as shown in figure 9. The elastic modulus of helical rib was calculated using Equation 1 by applying 20kN and the results are shown in Table 2 [4].

$$E = \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\Delta\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{A\Delta\varepsilon} \frac{\Delta P}{2\cos\phi} \quad (\Delta\varepsilon = \frac{\varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3}{2}) \quad (1)$$

Figure 9: Calculation of compressive and bending strain.

		Load	$\varepsilon_2 (\mu\varepsilon)$	$\varepsilon_3 (\mu\varepsilon)$	$\Delta\varepsilon (\mu\varepsilon)$	E(GPa)
Test	CT#4	20kN	-1620	-1932	-1776	99.1
	CT#11		-1452	-1976	-1714	102.7
	CT#14		-2238	-1374	-1806	97.4
FEA			-1621	-1763	-1692	104.1

Table 2: Comparison of test and analysis results – strain and elastic modulus at 20kN

5 CONCLUSIONS

Compression tests for the single unit cell of composite lattice structure were performed. Buckling and static analysis were performed and compared with the test results. The maximum load and failure mode of single unit cell were examined. As a result of the buckling analysis, it was confirmed that the compressive failure load is lower than critical buckling load. Static analysis was performed for the comparison of the test results, and the strain and longitudinal elastic modulus of the helical rib were compared with FEA results. The finite element analysis model for the knot region was modelled by separating ply and resin layers. The test method for single unit cell of composite lattice structure was proposed and the finite element analysis model was verified.

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